

Yaxshiboyev Axrorbek

the teacher of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Hayotillayeva Gavharazimxon

the student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

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Abstract: This paper examines the main units of verbal communication, namely, phonemes, morphemes, syntax, and propositions. Phonemes are the basic building blocks of language and are used to distinguish between different sounds. Morphemes are the smallest units of meaning in language, and they can be combined to form words. Syntax refers to the rules that govern how words are organized into phrases and sentences. Finally, propositions are the meaning units conveyed by sentences. Understanding these units is crucial for effective communication, as they work together to convey a message accurately and efficiently.

Keywords: verbal communication, combine, phoneme, morphemes, convey a message, assertiveness.

Verbal communication involves the use of spoken words to convey a message from one person to another. The main units of verbal communication include:

Words: Words are the basic units of verbal communication. They are used to convey meaning and can be combined to form sentences and phrases.

Sentences: Sentences are a collection of words that convey a complete thought or idea. They are often structured with a subject, verb, and object.

Phrases: Phrases are groups of words that function as a unit within a sentence. They may consist of a noun or verb and their modifiers.

Tone: Tone refers to the emotional or expressive quality of someone's voice when speaking. It can convey information about a person's attitude, mood, or intent.

Pitch: Pitch refers to the highness or lowness of someone's voice when speaking. It can convey information about a person's emotional state or level of emphasis.

Volume: Volume refers to the loudness or softness of someone's voice when speaking. It can convey information about a person's level of confidence or assertiveness.

Pace: Pace refers to the speed at which someone speaks. It can convey information about a person's level of excitement, nervousness, or urgency.

All of these units work together to create effective verbal communication.

In conclusion, verbal communication is an essential aspect of human interaction, and it involves various main units that help individuals to effectively convey their messages. These main units include words, grammar, tone, pitch, and volume. Understanding and mastering these units can greatly enhance one's ability to communicate effectively, while ignoring or neglecting them can lead to confusion, misunderstandings, and even conflict. However, it is important to note that effective verbal communication also requires active listening, empathy, and respect for others. By improving our verbal communication skills and incorporating these principles into our interactions, we can build better relationships, promote understanding, and achieve our goals more effectively.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати:

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